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Studies in n'th terms of infinite sequences of primes

Part I,II

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Preface

In research part (1) , we introduce a formula

$$D(n) = 36n^2 + 12n - 5, n \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ and } 5 \nmid D(n)$$

and analyses it. we shall repeat somehow what we need from the first part and then we develop (in the second part)

the ideas to get an original formula that under special substitution gives several variations each of which is function such that it's domain is \mathbb{Z}^+ and the range is an infinite set of only

Distinct primes of the form $24K-5$, $K \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ with no conditions, by this we solve an old historical interest in number theory subject

ABSTRACT

The object of this paper is to define a power function with domain \mathbb{N} and range is only of distinct infinite primes , So we have many n th terms of different infinite sequences of only different infinite primes .

Review

We proved in the first part of my research the following facts:

lemma (1)

let p be an odd prime, Then $(6/p) = (2/p) \cdot (3/p) = 1$

iff $P \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{24}$ or $P \equiv \pm 5 \pmod{24}$

P.f proof is given in the old theory and mentioned in the part (I) research.

Problem(1)

Let a and $b > 1$ be relatively prime integers, with b is odd, if $b = P_1 \cdot P_2 \dots P_r$ is the decomposition of b into odd primes (not necessarily distinct), then if the congruence $x^2 \equiv a \pmod{b}$ has a solution then $x^2 \equiv a \pmod{P_i}$ also has a solution.

$\forall i = 1, 2, \dots, r.$

p.f if $x^2 = a \pmod{b}$ has a solution

and P_i/b

then $x^2 = a \pmod{P_i}$ also has a solution.

$\forall i = 1, 2, \dots, r.$

lemma (2)

Define $D(n) = 36n^2 + 12n - 5, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

if $D(n) = P_1 \cdot P_2 \cdot \dots \cdot P_r$ is the decomposition of $D(n)$

in to odd primes (not necessarily distinct)

then $x^2 \equiv 6 \pmod{D(n)}$ has a solution implies

$(6/P_i) = 1, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, r.$

and $P_i \equiv -1, 1, -5, \text{ or } 5 \pmod{24}.$

P.f let $D(n) = 36n^2 + 12n - 5 = (6n+1)^2 - 6 = P_1 \cdot P_2 \cdot \dots \cdot P_r$

then the congruence

$(6n+1)^2 \equiv 6 \pmod{D(n)}$ implies for each P_i

$(6n+1)^2 \equiv 6 \pmod{P_i} \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \forall P_i/n.$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, r$

so $(6/P_i) = 1 \Rightarrow$ (by lemma (1))

$P_i \equiv -1, 1, -5 \text{ or } 5 \pmod{24}$

Theorem(1)

let $D(n) = 36n^2 + 12n - 5, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $5 \nmid D(n)$

if $D(n)$ is composite, then $D(n)$ is of the form $24M - 5, M \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, and also $\exists f, K$

positive integer such that f is the max integer that $24f \pm 1 \mid D(n)$

and K is the least integer that $24K \pm 5 \mid D(n)$

further more

$24f + 1$ or $24f - 1$ are integers and $24K - 5$ or $24K + 5$ are primes.

So the final form of $D(n) = (24f \pm 1)(24k \mp 5) = 24M - 5$, respectively, where $24K - 5$ or $24k + 5$ are primes.

p.f suppose that $D(n)$ is composite,

then $D(n) = P_1 \cdot P_2 \dots P_r$ where each P_i is of the form $24K \pm 1$ or $24K \pm 5$ as in

lemma (2).

Now at last the final multiplication of the above primes could be of the forms $24M + 1$ or $24M - 1$ or $24M + 5$ or $24M - 5$, apply on $D(n)$ we will have at last if Finally:

(1) $D(n) = 24M - 1, M \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ then

$$D(n) = 36n^2 + 12n - 5 = 24M - 1 \Rightarrow 9n^2 + 3n - 1 = 6M$$

the R.H.S is divisible by 3 while the L.H.S is not contradiction.

(2) $D(n) = 24M + 1, M \in \mathbb{Z}^+$,

$$\text{then } D(n) = 36n^2 + 12n - 5 = 24M + 1 \Rightarrow 36n^2 + 12n - 6 = 24M \Rightarrow$$

$$6n^2 + 2n - 1 = 4M, \text{ the L.H.S is odd while the R.H.S is even contradiction.}$$

(3) if $D(n) = 24M + 5, M \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ then

$$D(n) = 36n^2 + 12n - 5 = 24M + 5 \Rightarrow$$

$$36n^2 + 12n - 10 = 24M \Rightarrow 18n^2 + 6n - 5 = 12M$$

the L.H.S is odd while the R.H.S is even contradiction.

so what is remaining is that $D(n)$ is only in the

form $24M - 5, M \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ where $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ S.T $5 \nmid D(n)$

with the factors of $D(n)$ are only of the

form $(24K \pm 1)$ or $(24K \pm 5)$. Now if the factors of $D(n)$

i) if $D(n) = (24M_1 \pm 5)(24M_2 \pm 1)$ respectively then $D(n) = 24M + 5$

contradiction

ii) if $D(n) = (24M_1 \pm 1) (24 M_2 \pm 1)$ respectively

Then $D(n) = 24 M + 1$ contradiction

iii) if $D(n) = (24M_1 \pm 1) (24M_2 \mp 1)$ respectively

then $D(n) = 24M - 1$ not of the form $24M-5$ contradiction.

iv) if $D(n) = (24M_1 \pm 5) (24 M_2 \pm 5)$ then $D(n)$ is of the form $24M + 1$ not of the form $24M-5$ contradiction.

Also if $D(n) = (24M_1 \pm 5) (24 M_2 \mp 5)$ then $D(n)$ is of the form $24M-1$ not of the form $24M-5$, contradiction

Thus what is remaining is the final case of the

Composite $D(n) = (24M_1 \pm 1) (24 M_2 \mp 5) = 24M - 5$

i.e $D(n) = (24M_1-1)(24M_2 + 5)$ or

$D(n) = (24 M_1 + 1)(24 M_2 - 5)$ and $5 \nmid D(n)$, and $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

for an increasing of the integer $24M_1 \pm 1$ by the factors $24 M + 1$ until the final form of

$D(n) = (24f \pm 1)(24K \mp 5)$

respectively where $24K - 5$ or $24K + 5$ are primes.

Theorem (2)

let $D(n) = 36n^2+12n - 5 = 12n(3n+1)-5$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

then $5 \nmid D(n)$ iff $n \equiv 1, 2$ or $4 \pmod{5}$

p.f any positive integer n is of the form

(1) $n = 5m \rightarrow 5/n \rightarrow 5/D(n)$ or

2) $n = 5m+1 \rightarrow 5 \nmid n(3n+1) \rightarrow 5 \nmid D(n)$ or

$$3) n = 5m+2 \rightarrow 5 \nmid n(3n+1) \rightarrow 5 \nmid D(n) \text{ or}$$

$$4) n = 5m+3 \rightarrow 5 \nmid n(3n+1) \rightarrow 5 \nmid D(n) \text{ or}$$

$$5) n = 5m+4 \rightarrow 5 \nmid n(3n+1) \rightarrow 5 \nmid D(n)$$

thus $5 \nmid D(n)$ iff $n \equiv 1, 2 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$

now here we have finish what we need from our first research, and we will start our new part II research by the following:

lemma(3)

given $n \equiv 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

$a = n(3n+1)$ and so $D(n) = 12n(3n+1) - 5 =$

$12a - 5$, then the equation

$D(n) = 12a - 5 = (24x + 1)(24y - 5)$ of

two variables $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}^-$

has only the trivial solution

$x=0, y = \frac{a}{2}$ iff $D(n)$ is prime.

p.f

let $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, $n \equiv 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$ be given

and $D(n) = 12n(3n+1) - 5 = 12a - 5$, $a = n(3n+1)$

Then $D(n) = P$ is prime \leftrightarrow the linear equation

$D(n) = (24x + 1)(24y - 5)$, $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}^-$

of two variables x, y gives only the trivial

factors of $D(n)$ which are 1 and so $X=0$

and the other factor is $D(n)$ itself and

so $y = \frac{a}{2}$ on \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}^- , thus the equation

$D(n) = 12a - 5 = (24x+1)(24y-5)$ on \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}
 has only the trivial solution $x = 0, y = \frac{a}{2}$
 and no other solution for $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}$ exists.

what we need to continue the following

Definition: given the following constants

let $n_0 \equiv 1$ or $4 \pmod{5}$

$$a_0 = n_0(3n_0+1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 D(n_0) &= 12n_0(3n_0+1) - 5 = 12a_0 - 5 \\
 &= 36n_0^2 + 12n_0 - 5 \quad \text{is known prime } P. \\
 J &= 1, 2, 3, \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

n_J is to be defined also such that $\exists d_J \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

constant depends on n_J such that:

$$n_J \in \mathbb{Z}^+, n_J \equiv 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5},$$

$$\text{and } D(n_J) = 12n_J(3n_J + 1) - 5 = 12a_0 d_J - 5$$

is well defined.

thus all of $n_0, a_0, P = D(n_0), J \Rightarrow$

n_j, d_j are constants and fixed known
 under suitable conditions are to be given later.
 and only variables are x and z/z'
 after we will give theorems 3,4,5
 to reach to theorem 6 which states that

Theorem 6:

given $n_0 \equiv 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$, $n_0 \in \mathbb{Z}^+$
 $a_0 = n_0(3n_0 + 1)$ such that

$$P = D(n_0) = 12n_0(3n_0 + 1) - 5 = 12a_0 - 5 \text{ is}$$

known prime.

$$\text{define } n_j = \frac{(3n_0)^{(3^j)}}{3}$$

then $n_j \equiv 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$

also define

$$d_J = \frac{(3n_0)^{\binom{J}{3}} ((3n_0)^{\binom{J}{3}} + 1)}{3a}$$

Set $J= 1,2,3,\dots$

Thus we will have

$$D(n_J) = 4(3n_0)^{\binom{J}{3}} ((3n_0)^{\binom{J}{3}} + 1) - 5 = 12a_0 d_J - 5$$

is well defined infinite sequence of only
distinct of primes for each $J = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

to prove this final theorem (6) we start first
proving that $d_J \in \mathbb{Z}^+$:

Note that $3a_0 = 3n_0(3n_0 + 1)$, but

$$3n_0 / (3n_0)^{(3^J)} \longrightarrow (1)$$

And

$$3n_0 \equiv -1 \pmod{3n_0 + 1}$$

$$\Rightarrow (3n_0)^{(3^J)} \equiv (-1)^{(3^J)} = -1 \pmod{3n_0 + 1} \longrightarrow (2)$$

$$3n_0(3n_0 + 1) / (3n_0)^{(3^J)} ((3n_0)^{(3^J)} + 1)$$

so from (1)(2) we have

Thus $d_j \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ for each $J = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

second we prove that $D(n_j) = 12a_0 d_j - 5$

is well defined as follow : under defining

$$n_j = \frac{(3n_0)^{(3^J)}}{3} \text{ when } n_0 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$$

$$\Rightarrow 3n_0 \equiv 3 \pmod{5} \Rightarrow$$

$$(3n_0)^{(3^J)} \equiv 3^{(3^J)} \pmod{5} \implies$$

$$n_J = \frac{(3n_0)^{(3^J)}}{3} \equiv 3^{(3^J)-1} \equiv 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$$

Thus if $n_0 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$ we have

$$n_J \equiv 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5} \longrightarrow (3)$$

second if $n_0 \equiv 4 \pmod{5} \implies$

$$3n_0 \equiv 3 \cdot 4 \equiv 3 \cdot (-1) \pmod{5}$$

$$(3n_0)^{(3^J)} \equiv 3^{(3^J)} \cdot (-1)^{(3^J)} = -1 \cdot 3^{(3^J)} \pmod{5}$$

$$n_J = \frac{(3n_0)^{(3^J)}}{3} \equiv -1 \cdot 3^{(3^J)-1} \equiv -1 \text{ or } -4 \equiv$$

4 or 1 $\pmod{5}$ respectively

Thus

$$n_J = \frac{(3n_0)^{\binom{J}{3}}}{3} \equiv 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$$

whenever $n_0 \equiv 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$

thus $D(n_J) = 12 n_J(3n_J + 1) - 5$

we have $5 \nmid D(n_J)$.

what is remaining to prove before
theorems 3, 4,5 is that

$$D(n_J) = 12 n_J (3 n_J + 1) - 5 = 12a_0d_J - 5$$

is well defined where $n_J = 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$

$$\text{but } D(n_J) = D\left(\frac{(3n_0)^{\binom{J}{3}}}{3}\right) =$$

\Rightarrow

$$= \cancel{12}^4 \left(\frac{(3n_0)^{(3^J)}}{\cancel{3}_1} \right) \left(\cancel{3} \frac{(3n_0)^{(3^J)}}{\cancel{3}_1} + 1 \right) - 5$$

$$= 4 \left((3n_0)^{(3^J)} \right) \left((3n_0)^{(3^J)} + 1 \right) - 5$$

= $12a_0 d_J - 5$ (is consistent and well defined)

$$= \cancel{12}^4 a_0 \left[\frac{\left((3n_0)^{(3^J)} \right) \left((3n_0)^{(3^J)} + 1 \right)}{\cancel{3} a_0} \right] - 5$$

= $D(n_j)$, $J = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

now the coming theorems 3,4,5 will

prove that $D(n_j)$ is prime whenever $D(n_0)$ is prime.

Theorem (3)

given $n_0 \equiv 1$ or $4 \pmod{5}$

$$a_0 = n_0 (3n_0 + 1)$$

such that $D(n_0) = 12n_0(3n_0 + 1) - 5 = 12a_0 - 5$

is known prime, for each $J=1,2,3,\dots$

let d_J, n_J be defined as in theorem (6)

are regarded as constants in each J step

Then consider the linear equation

$12a_0 - 5 = D(n_0) = (24x + 1) (24y - 5)$ of two variables

x, y on \mathbb{Z} , which will have

the solution $x=0, y = \frac{a_0}{2}$ only iff

$$D(n_0)d_J = (12a_0 - 5)d_J = (24x+1) (24y-5) d_J$$

has only the same trivial solution

$$x = 0, y_0 = \frac{a_0}{2}$$

P.f given the prime equation

$$(1) \leftarrow D(n_0) = 12n_0(3n_0+1) - 5 = 12a_0 - 5 =$$

$(24x+1)(24y-5)$ has only the trivial

solution $x = 0, y = \frac{a_0}{2}$ on \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}

\leftrightarrow the equation

$$D(n_0)d_j = (12a_0 - 5) d_j =$$

$(24x+1)(24y-5)d_j$ would have the same

trivial solution only, for if $\exists X_1 \neq X_0$

$y_1 \neq y_0$ another solution

Then divide the last equation by $d_j \neq 0$

contradicts equation (1) since $D(n_0)$ is prime.

Theorem(4)

Let $n_0, a_0, D(n_0) = P_0, d_J, n_J$ be defined as in

Theorem(6) for each J step, then the linear

equation $D(n_0)d_J = P_0d_J = (24x + 1)(24y - 5)d_J$

$$= (12a_0 - 5) d_J$$

has only the trivial solution $X_0 = 0, y_0 = \frac{a_0}{2}$ on z/z'

iff $D(n_J) = 12a_0d_J - 5 = (24x + 1)(24H - 5)$

has only the trivial solution.

$X = X_0 = 0$ and $H = y_0d_J = \frac{a_0}{2} d_J$

on z/z'

p.f.

the linear equation $D(n_o) = 12a_o - 5 = (24x+1)(24y-5)$

has only the trivial solution $x_o = 0, y_o = \frac{a_o}{2}$

$$\begin{aligned} \iff P_o d_J &= D(n_o) d_J = (24x + 1)(24y-5) d_J \\ &= (12a_o - 5) d_J \end{aligned}$$

has only the same trivial solution.

$x_o=0, y_o = \frac{a_o}{2}$ on \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}^* , ($a_o = n_o(3n_o+1)$)

$$\iff D(n_o) d_J = 12a_o d_J - 5d_J =$$

$$= 24y d_J (24x+1) - 5d_J (24x+1)$$

has only the same trivial solution \iff the linear

equation $12a_o d_J - 24y d_J (24x+1) = 5d_J - 5d_J (24x+1)$

has the same trivial solution x_o, y_o on \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}^*

\implies define now variables C, E beside the variables x,y.

These 4 variables are defined on z/z'

thus the linear equations become as follow

$$12a_0d_j - 24yd_j(24x+1) = 5d_j - 5d_j(24x+1) = C$$

$$= 5 - 5(24E+1) \rightarrow (1)$$

Now an only solution $x_0 = 0$ for x and $y_0 = \frac{a_0}{2}$

for $y \iff$ only solution for C is $C_0 = 0 \iff$

only solution for E is $E_0 = 0$ on z/z' .

These equivalent statements imply that only solution

for C is $c=0 \iff x = E = 0$ and $y = \frac{a_0}{2}$

so we can replace the dummy variable $E=0$ by

$X=0 \iff$ the linear equation of (1) is then

restricted to the following equalities

$$12a_0d_J - 24yd_J(24x+1) = 5-5(24E + 1) = 5-5(24x+1)=0$$

which has only the trivial solution

$$x_0 = E = 0 \text{ and } y_0 = \frac{a_0}{2}$$

$$\iff 12a_0d_J - 5 = 24yd_J(24x+1) - 5(24x + 1)$$

has only the trivial solution x_0, y_0

$$\iff 12a_0d_J - 5 = (24x+1)(24yd_J - 5)$$

Has only the trivial solution $x_0 = 0, y_0 = \frac{a_0}{2}$ on z/\bar{z} .

but then $D(n_J) = 12a_0d_J - 5$ is well defined

as showed before \iff the linear equation

$$D(n_J) = 12a_0d_J - 5 = (24x+1)(24yd_J - 5)$$

has only the trivial solution $x_0 = 0$, $y_0 = \frac{a_0}{2}$ on \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z} .

but d_J is constants in each J step.

so if we introduce new variable $H \in \mathbb{Z}/\mathbb{Z}$

then (2) $\leftarrow D(n_J) = (24x+1)(24yd_J - 5) = (24x + 1) (24H - 5)$

has only the trivial solution $x_0 = 0$, $y_0 = \frac{a_0}{2} \iff$

$x_0 = 0$ and $H_J = \frac{a_0}{2}d_J$ is the only solution of (2)

Theorem(5)

let $n_0, a_0, D(n_0), d_J, n_J$ be given constants

S. T $n_0 \equiv 1$ or $4 \pmod{5}$

$a_0 = n_0(3n_0 + 1)$

$D(n_0) = 12n_0(3n_0 + 1) - 5$ be known prime

$$n_J = \frac{(3n_0)^{(3^J)}}{3}, \text{ thus } n_J = 1 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{5}$$

$$d_J = \frac{\left((3n_0)^{(3^J)} \right) \left((3n_0)^{(3^J)} + 1 \right)}{3a_0} \in \mathbf{Z}^+$$

for each $J = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

define the variables x, H_J on \mathbf{z}/\mathbf{z}

then $D(n_J) = 12n_J(3n_J + 1) - 5 = 12a_0d_J - 5$

is prime of the form $24H_J - 5$

where $H_J = \frac{a_0}{2} d_J$.

P.f we had prove in thenem (4) that the equation

$$D(n_J) = (24x + 1) (24 H_J - 5), \quad x, H_J \in \mathbf{z}/\mathbf{z}$$

has only the trivial solution $X=0$

$H_J = y_0 d_J = \frac{a_0}{2} d_J$ for only variables
 X, y, H on z/z'

and so from the last lemma. $D(n_J)$ is
prime whenever $D(n_0)$ is prime

and $n_0 \equiv 1$ or $4 \pmod{5}$ for each $J = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

after this theorem(5), then theorem (6)
is stated before, we have then an application
to theorem (6) as follows:

Theorem (7) (An application to theorem(6))

special cases of theorem(6) are in the

Following:

(1) $n_0 = 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, $D(n_0) = D(1) = 12 \times 4 - 5$
 $= 43$ is prime. Thus

$$D_1(J) = D(n_J) = D\left(\frac{(3n_0)^{(3^J)}}{3}\right) =$$
$$4\left(3^{(3^J)}\right)\left(3^{(3^J)} + 1\right) - 5, \quad J = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

is infinite sequence of only distinct primes.

(2) let $n_0 = 4 \equiv 4 \pmod{5} \implies D(n_0) = 12 \times 4 \times 13 - 5 = 619$

which is prime, thus $D(n_J)$ is prime and so

$$D_2(J) = D\left(\frac{(3n_0)^{\binom{J}{3}}}{3}\right) = D(n_J) = D\left(\frac{12^{\binom{J}{3}}}{3}\right) =$$

$$4\left(12^{\binom{J}{3}}\right)\left(12^{\binom{J}{3}} + 1\right) - 5 \quad , \quad J = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

is an infinite sequence of only distinct primes.

Note: easy to prove that.

(1) no common prime in these two sequences.

(2) show that the sequence

$$D_3(J) = D(n_J) = 4\left(33^{\binom{J}{3}}\right)\left(33^{\binom{J}{3}} + 1\right) - 5$$

$J = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

is an infinite sequence of primes.

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NOTE: about physics, there are conjectures in physics that are true from theoretical point of view such that they are helping in huge part of medical theory without applying muscle efforts from the patient. So it will improve and develop the general health .

It had proven in lab with simple equipment's the benefit of the medical physics experiment for example we got a good deep respiration as one result from different benefits for long period .

All of these claims could be proved through lab experiments in case of simple methods and finances.

APPLICATION OF MATH AND PHYSICS RESEARCHES

There are conjectures related to the given researches that concern the space theory that could be useful .

NOTE; there are conjecture concerning the initial steps of the borning universe with explanation the periodic and cyclic phenomenon .

NOTE ; all of the previous conjectures are logically convinced subjects and most of them could be proved in lab with low budget .

With Regards

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